

Scientometric Map of Loet Leydesdorff

Jie Li

National Science Library,
Chinese Academy of Sciences

lijie_jerry@126.com

<http://blog.sciencenet.cn/u/jerrycueb>

Contents

Date Collection	2
Annual trends.....	4
Journals	5
Citing Journals	5
Cited Journals	8
Journals dual-overlay	10
Collaboration Analysis	11
Authors collaboration	11
Institutions collaboration	12
Countries/Regions collaboration.....	12
Topics analysis	15
Author keywords analysis	15
Terms analysis.....	16
Citation analysis.....	18
Citing articles analysis.....	18
Documents bibliographic coupling	18
Direct citation network (CitNetExplorer).....	20
Direct citation network (HistCite).....	23
Cited articles analysis	24
RPYS analysis	24
Authors co-citation analysis.....	25
References co-citation analysis (VOSviewer).....	26
References co-citation analysis (CiteSpace).....	27
Scientometric mapping tools	32
CiteSpace.....	32
VOSviewer.....	32
CitNetExplorer	32
NetsCity	32
leydesdorff.net.....	32
HistCite	32
Appendix	33

Loet Leydesdorff (Ph.D. Sociology, M.A. Philosophy, and M.Sc. Biochemistry) is Professor at the Amsterdam School of Communications Research (ASCoR) of the University of Amsterdam. He is Visiting Professor of the Institute of Scientific and Technical Information of China (ISTIC) in Beijing and Honorary Fellow of the Science and Technology Policy Research Unit (SPRU) of the University of Sussex. He has published extensively in systems theory, social network analysis, scientometrics, and the sociology of innovation (see for a list of publications at <http://www.leydesdorff.net/list.htm>). With Henry Etzkowitz, he initiated a series of workshops, conferences, and special issues about the Triple Helix of University-Industry-Government Relations. He received the Derek de Solla Price Award for Scientometrics and Informetrics in 2003 and held “The City of Lausanne” Honor Chair at the School of Economics, Université de Lausanne, in 2005. Since 2014, the Web of Science lists him as a highly-cited author at <https://clarivate.com/hcr/>

Source: <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-7835-3098>

▪ Data Collection

The screenshot displays the Web of Science search interface. At the top right, there are navigation links: Tools, Searches and alerts, Search History, and Marked List. Below this is a header bar with 'Select a database' set to 'Web of Science Core Collection' and a button for 'Learn about alerting enhancements!'. The main search area has tabs for 'Basic Search', 'Author Search^{BETA}', 'Cited Reference Search', and 'Advanced Search'. The 'Basic Search' tab is active. It features two search input fields: the first contains 'E-2903-2010' and is set to 'Author Identifiers'; the second contains 'Example: oil spill* mediterranean' and is set to 'Topic'. A 'Search' button and 'Search tips' link are to the right. Below the search fields are options for '+ Add row' and 'Reset'. A 'Timespan' dropdown is set to 'All years (1900 - 2020)'. Under 'More settings', there are checkboxes for 'Web of Science Core Collection: Citation Indexes', 'Science Citation Index Expanded (SCI-EXPANDED) --1900-present', and 'Social Science Citation Index (SSCI) --1900-present'. An 'Auto-suggest publication names' dropdown is set to 'On'.

Fig. 1 Data collection

Web of Science InCites Journal Citation Reports Essential Science Indicators EndNote Publons Kopernio Sign In Help English

Web of Science

Clarivate Analytics

Search Tools Searches and alerts Search History Marked List

Results: 338
(from Web of Science Core Collection)

You searched for: AUTHOR
IDENTIFIERS: (E-2903-2010)
Timespan: All years. Indexes: SCI-EXPANDED, SSCI.
...Less
Create an alert

Refine Results

Search within results for...

Filter results by:

- Highly Cited in Field (6)
- Open Access (79)

Refine

Publication Years

Sort by: Date Times Cited Usage Count Relevance More

Select Page Export... Add to Marked List

- Synergy in the knowledge base of US innovation systems at national, state, and regional levels: The contributions of high-tech manufacturing and knowledge-intensive services**

By: Leydesdorff, Loet; Wagner, Caroline S.; Porto-Gomez, Igone; et al.
JOURNAL OF THE ASSOCIATION FOR INFORMATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY Volume: 70 Issue: 10 Pages: 1108-1123 Published: OCT 2019

Findit NCKU Free Full Text from Publisher View Abstract

Times Cited: 1
(from Web of Science Core Collection)
Usage Count
- Can topic models be used in research evaluations? Reproducibility, validity, and reliability when compared with semantic maps**

By: Hecking, Tobias; Leydesdorff, Loet
RESEARCH EVALUATION Volume: 28 Issue: 3 Pages: 263-272 Published: JUL 2019

Findit NCKU Full Text from Publisher View Abstract

Times Cited: 0
(from Web of Science Core Collection)
Usage Count
- The integrated impact indicator revisited(I3*): a non-parametric alternative to the journal impact factor**

By: Leydesdorff, Loet; Bornmann, Lutz; Adams, Jonathan
SCIENTOMETRICS Volume: 119 Issue: 3 Pages: 1669-1694 Published: JUN 2019

Findit NCKU Free Full Text from Publisher View Abstract

Times Cited: 0
(from Web of Science Core Collection)
Usage Count
- Does the public discuss other topics on climate change than researchers? A comparison of explorative**

Times Cited: 1

Analyze Results
Create Citation Report

Fig. 2 Results of the data

Table 1 Main Information about the collection (6 Highly Cited in Field, 79 Open Access)

Description	Results
Documents	338
Sources (Journals, Books, etc.)	64
Keywords Plus (ID)	412
Author's Keywords (DE)	493
Period	1980 - 2019
Average citations per documents	41.21
Authors	178
Author Appearances	737
Authors of single-authored documents	3
Authors of multi-authored documents	175
Single-authored documents	94
Documents per Author	1.9
Authors per Document	0.527
Co-Authors per Documents	2.18
Collaboration Index	0.717
Document types	
ARTICLE	279
ARTICLE; PROCEEDINGS PAPER	5
BOOK REVIEW	6
CORRECTION	1
EDITORIAL MATERIAL	17
LETTER	23
MEETING ABSTRACT	1
NEWS ITEM	1
NOTE	2
REVIEW	3

■ Annual trends

Fig. 3 Publications trend of Loet Leydesdorff

Fig. 4 Citations trend of Loet Leydesdorff

Table 2 Publication and citation trends of Loet Leydesdorff

#	Year	Recs	Percent	TLCS	TGCS	#	Year	Recs	Percent	TLCS	TGCS
1	1980	1	0.3	0	0	20	2001	4	1.2	6	30
2	1981	1	0.3	1	3	21	2002	5	1.5	24	74
3	1982	1	0.3	2	2	22	2003	7	2.1	31	236
4	1984	1	0.3	2	2	23	2004	3	0.9	31	184
5	1986	1	0.3	37	64	24	2005	12	3.6	77	838
6	1987	5	1.5	19	109	25	2006	12	3.6	153	1111
7	1988	1	0.3	0	0	26	2007	13	3.8	45	520
8	1989	5	1.5	66	219	27	2008	13	3.8	98	713
9	1990	4	1.2	44	103	28	2009	19	5.6	168	1147
10	1991	4	1.2	43	80	29	2010	19	5.6	167	1141
11	1992	5	1.5	26	39	30	2011	22	6.5	179	955
12	1993	3	0.9	33	95	31	2012	18	5.3	108	782
13	1994	7	2.1	50	139	32	2013	26	7.7	75	681
14	1995	2	0.6	8	10	33	2014	24	7.1	73	520
15	1996	4	1.2	9	105	34	2015	21	6.2	27	391
16	1997	5	1.5	43	151	35	2016	18	5.3	43	228
17	1998	4	1.2	18	367	36	2017	17	5	15	110
18	1999	2	0.6	11	31	37	2018	11	3.3	4	44
19	2000	7	2.1	78	2690	38	2019	11	3.3	3	16

- **Journals**
- **Citing Journals**

Fig. 5 Journals bibliographic coupling analysis (Nodes size was appropriate with number of publications, and the color is shown the average publication year of the journal)

Note: journal of the American society for information science (JASIST), journal of informetrics (JOI), scientometrics (SCI) and jasss-the journal of artificial societies and social simulation (JASSS).

Table 3 Citing journals of Loet Leydesdorff

Journals	Documents	Citations	Avg. pub. Year	Avg. citations
SCI	87	2416	2005.94	27.77
JASIST	85	3872	2010.78	45.55
JOI	41	1451	2013.49	35.39
RESEARCH POLICY	15	4195	2002.00	279.67
PROFESIONAL DE LA INFORMACION	8	94	2013.50	11.75
SOCIAL SCIENCE INFORMATION SUR LES SCIENCES SOCIALES	8	78	2002.38	9.75
SYSTEMS RESEARCH AND BEHAVIORAL SCIENCE	6	79	2005.00	13.17
TECHNOLOGICAL FORECASTING AND SOCIAL CHANGE	6	144	2012.17	24.00
PLOS ONE	5	109	2014.40	21.80
RESEARCH EVALUATION	4	64	2013.50	16.00
SCIENCE TECHNOLOGY & HUMAN VALUES	4	79	1990.25	19.75
TECHNOLOGY ANALYSIS & STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT	4	78	2008.00	19.50
JOURNAL OF DOCUMENTATION	3	78	2002.67	26.00
KYBERNETES	3	15	2008.67	5.00
MINERVA	3	241	2007.67	80.33
CURRENT SCIENCE	2	20	2000.50	10.00
EMBO REPORTS	2	40	2014.50	20.00
ENTROPY	2	35	2009.00	17.50
JASSS	2	7	2003.00	3.50
JOURNAL OF SOCIAL AND EVOLUTIONARY SYSTEMS	2	20	1994.00	10.00
PUBLIC UNDERSTANDING OF SCIENCE	2	83	2007.50	41.50
RECHERCHE	2	3	1987.00	1.50
SCIENCE AND PUBLIC POLICY	2	9	2014.00	4.50
SOCIAL STUDIES OF SCIENCE	2	40	2002.00	20.00

Fig. 6 Location of citing journals on the global journals map

Fig. 10 Location of cited journals of on the global journals map (Rao-Stirling diversity is: 0.1538)

Table 4 High cited sources the citing papers

Journals	Links	Total link strength	Citations
SCIENTOMETRICS	82	41720	1622
JASIST	82	40219	1498
RES POLICY	82	20168	733
J INFORMETR	80	17109	535
SCIENCE	82	6934	211
SOC NETWORKS	81	3972	163
NATURE	82	4155	142
SOC STUD SCI	82	3994	141
SCI PUBL POLICY	82	3569	112
SOC SCI INFORM	82	3436	110
RES EVALUAT	77	3058	83
PLOS ONE	67	2882	76
P NATL ACAD SCI USA	73	2664	73
TECHNICAL CHANGE EC	76	1747	67
BELL SYST TECH J	79	1545	65
INFORM PROCESS LETT	79	2051	61
ANNU REV INFORM SCI	79	2655	58
INFORM PROCESS MANAG	73	2340	58
EVOLUTIONARY EC CHAO	73	1515	57
AM ECON REV	79	1888	55
INT J GEN SYST	72	1488	54
CHALLENGE SCIENTOMET	78	1340	53
PSYCHOMETRIKA	79	1627	53
INTELLECTUAL SOCIAL	82	1660	51

- Journals dual-overlay

Fig. 11 Journals dual overlay map of Loet Leydesdorff

- Collaboration Analysis
- Authors collaboration

Fig. 12 Authors collaboration network of Loet Leydesdorff

Table 5 Co-authors of Loet Leydesdorff

Authors	Links	Documents	Avg. pub. year	Avg. citations
Bornmann, Lutz	28	58	2014.74	23.40
Wagner, Caroline S.	16	23	2013.26	45.17
Zhou, Ping	4	13	2009.92	47.31
Park, Han Woo	8	12	2012.17	41.33
Rafols, Ismael	10	12	2011.92	108.25
Opthof, Tobias	3	10	2011.80	47.30
Ivanova, Inga A.	5	9	2015.56	11.56
Hellsten, Iina	8	7	2011.14	27.14
Comins, Jordan A.	8	6	2017.17	3.17
De Nooy, Wouter	8	6	2013.67	10.50
Marx, Werner	7	6	2014.33	22.17
Rotolo, Daniele	6	6	2014.83	16.67
Van Den Besselaar, Peter	2	6	2006.67	33.50
Wouters, Paul	3	6	2001.00	17.50
De Moya-anegon, Felix	4	5	2012.60	43.80
Dolfsma, Wilfred	2	5	2008.80	32.40
Heimeriks, Gaston	5	5	2012.40	12.00
Lucio-arias, Diana	2	5	2009.80	31.60
Meyer, Martin	1	5	2007.80	69.00

▪ **Institutions collaboration**

Fig. 13 Institutions collaboration network of Loet Leydesdorff

▪ **Countries/Regions collaboration**

Fig. 14 Countries collaboration network of Loet Leydesdorff

Table 6 Countries/regions have collaborated with Loet Leydesdorff (Documents>1)

Countries/Regions	Links	Documents	Avg. pub. Year	Avg. citations
NETHERLANDS	28	289	2010.50	44.83
GERMANY	12	63	2014.25	24.19
USA	15	52	2011.88	88.35
ENGLAND	9	31	2012.87	61.29
PEOPLES R CHINA	4	20	2010.95	33.95
BELGIUM	12	14	2010.86	26.29
SOUTH KOREA	4	14	2012.21	38.71
SPAIN	8	13	2013.77	31.54
RUSSIA	5	10	2015.50	12.10
SWITZERLAND	3	9	2008.22	69.78
AUSTRALIA	9	4	2008.00	42.75
HUNGARY	2	4	2011.25	21.25
ITALY	4	4	2015.25	11.00
NORWAY	3	4	2015.00	16.75
SWEDEN	5	4	2013.00	44.50
FINLAND	8	3	2008.00	36.00
IRELAND	2	2	2017.50	6.00
MEXICO	4	2	2006.00	13.00
SCOTLAND	1	2	2010.50	79.00

ID	Agglomeration	Country	Publications ▼
AD8361	AMSTERDAM	NETHERLANDS	324
AD4662	MUNICH	GERMANY	55
AAPOLY23731	BRIGHTON	UNITED-KINGDOM	21
AD13304	COLUMBUS	UNITED-STATES	15
AD16876	WASHINGTON-BETHESDA	UNITED-STATES	13
AD2074	BEIJING	CHINA	13
AD1081	LEUVEN	BELGIUM	11
AD9995	TAEGU	SOUTH-KOREA	11
AD8563	UTRECHT	NETHERLANDS	9
AD4957	STUTT GART	GERMANY	7
AAPOINT20175	VLADIVOSTOK	RUSSIA	6
AD12830	BLOOMINGTON	UNITED-STATES	6
AD8483	ROTTERDAM-LEIDEN-DELFT-DEN HAAG	NETHERLANDS	6
AD10167	MADRID	SPAIN	5
AD15709	PHILADELPHIA	UNITED-STATES	5
AD2144	HANGZHOU	CHINA	5
AD4490	KARLSRUHE	GERMANY	5

Fig. 15 Countries/regions collaboration network on the world map

Note: Visualized by <http://37.187.79.5/netscitypg/index.php>

Fig. 16 Cities collaboration network on the world map

Fig. 19 Keywords average publications year of Loet Leydesdorff

Fig. 20 Keywords average citations of Loet Leydesdorff

- Terms analysis

VOSviewer

VOSviewer

Fig. 21 Terms analysis of the publications (terms were from titles and abstracts of the publications)

Table 7 High cited papers in each cluster

Documents	Cluster	Citations	Documents	Cluster	Citations	Documents	Cluster	Citations	Documents	Cluster	Citations
Rafols (2010)	1	207	Etzkowitz (2000)	2	2380	Wagner (2005)	3	436	Leydesdorff (1998)	4	177
Rafols (2012)	1	204	Etzkowitz (1998)	2	181	Zhou (2006)	3	311	Leydesdorff (1989)	4	107
Mingers (2015)	1	121	Leydesdorff (2000a)	2	171	Leydesdorff (2009e)	3	303	Leydesdorff (2006e)	4	103
Leydesdorff (2011e)	1	119	Leydesdorff (2006)	2	145	Leydesdorff (2007c)	3	222	Leydesdorff (1997a)	4	103
Opthof (2010)	1	117	Leydesdorff (2011n)	2	107	Leydesdorff (2006b)	3	201	Leydesdorff (1987b)	4	84
Leydesdorff (2009b)	1	109	Leydesdorff (2003a)	2	100	Leydesdorff (2008b)	3	157	Lucio-Arias (2008)	4	79
Leydesdorff (2011l)	1	105	Leydesdorff (2003)	2	99	Leydesdorff (2008g)	3	150	Park (2005)	4	77
Leydesdorff (2013h)	1	103	Park (2010)	2	97	Abbasi (2012)	3	140	Leydesdorff (1990b)	4	71
Bornmann (2012)	1	95	Leydesdorff (2006a)	2	95	Rafols (2009)	3	110	Van Den Besselaar (1996)	4	64
Leydesdorff (2011a)	1	91	Leydesdorff (2006f)	2	92	Leydesdorff (2009g)	3	98	Leydesdorff (1986)	4	64
Leydesdorff (2010)	1	91	Leydesdorff (2009c)	2	80	Leydesdorff (2005d)	3	98	Leydesdorff (2006d)	4	63
Bornmann (2013b)	1	81	Kwon (2012)	2	64	Leydesdorff (2008h)	3	90	Leydesdorff (1994c)	4	62
Leydesdorff (2011j)	1	80	Leydesdorff (2010d)	2	64	Egghe (2009)	3	76	Leydesdorff (2004a)	4	59
Leydesdorff (2010a)	1	67	Lengyel (2011)	2	56	Leydesdorff (2008c)	3	71	Leydesdorff (2005c)	4	57
Leydesdorff (2010f)	1	66	Leydesdorff (2010i)	2	51	Leydesdorff (2010c)	3	65	Leydesdorff (2005e)	4	57
Leydesdorff (2014f)	1	62	Leydesdorff (2011i)	2	49	Leydesdorff (2009)	3	65	Amsterdamska (1989)	4	56
Leydesdorff (2012g)	1	53	Leydesdorff (2010g)	2	49	Leydesdorff (2004)	3	65	Leydesdorff (1993b)	4	55
Halfman (2010)	1	53	Dolfsma (2009)	2	46	Leydesdorff (2007e)	3	64	Leydesdorff (1991)	4	44
Van Den Besselaar (2009)	1	53	Frenken (2000)	2	45	Leydesdorff (2004b)	3	60	Leydesdorff (1989b)	4	33
Leydesdorff (2013a)	1	52	Leydesdorff (2005b)	2	41	Leydesdorff (2008d)	3	53	Wouters (1994)	4	32
Leydesdorff (2012e)	1	49	Leydesdorff (2000)	2	41	Leydesdorff (2007d)	3	49	Leydesdorff (2000b)	4	27
Marx (2014)	1	48	Ivanova (2014)	2	37	Leydesdorff (2011f)	3	46	Leydesdorff (2002c)	4	26
Chen (2014)	1	48	Leydesdorff (1997c)	2	35	Wagner (2015a)	3	44	Leydesdorff (1996a)	4	24
Bornmann (2013c)	1	48	Leydesdorff (2007f)	2	33	Park (2013)	3	44	Leydesdorff (2002a)	4	23
Leydesdorff (2011)	1	47	Lucio-Arias (2009a)	2	31	Leydesdorff (2007g)	3	44	Leydesdorff (1994)	4	21
Bornmann (2011a)	1	47	Strand (2013)	2	30	Hellsten (2010)	3	42	Park (2016)	4	20
Bornmann (2010a)	1	47	Leydesdorff (2010b)	2	30	Leydesdorff (2013k)	3	41	Lucio-Arias (2009)	4	19
Bornmann (2011)	1	45	Leydesdorff (2013e)	2	28	Leydesdorff (2009a)	3	40	Lucio-Arias (2007)	4	19
Leydesdorff (2011g)	1	43	Leydesdorff (1993)	2	26	Leydesdorff (2008f)	3	38	Leydesdorff (2003e)	4	19
Bornmann (2014)	1	40	Leydesdorff (2014g)	2	25	Park (2009)	3	37	Leydesdorff (1987a)	4	19

Direct citation network (CitNetExplorer)

Fig. 24 Direct citation network of TOP 100 high cited publications of Loet Leydesdorff

Fig. 25 Direct citation network of TOP 100 high cited publications from blue cluster

Fig. 28 Direct citation network of 13 publications from orange cluster

Table 8 Papers from the orange cluster

Authors	Title	Year
Wagner, Cs; Leydesdorff, L	seismology as a dynamic, distributed area of scientific research	2003
Wagner, Cs; Leydesdorff, L	network structure, self-organization, and the growth of international collaboration in science	2005
Leydesdorff, L; Wagner, Cs	international collaboration in science and the formation of a core group	2008
Abbasi, A; Hossain, L; Leydesdorff, L	betweenness centrality as a driver of preferential attachment in the evolution of research collaboration networks	2012
Leydesdorff, L; Wagner, Cs; Park, Hw; Adams, J	international collaboration in science: the global map and the network	2013
Park, Hw; Leydesdorff, L	decomposing social and semantic networks in emerging "big data" research	2013
Leydesdorff, L; Park, Hw; Wagner, C	international coauthorship relations in the social sciences citation index: is internationalization leading the network?	2014
Adams, J; Gurney, K; Hook, D; Leydesdorff, L	international collaboration clusters in africa	2014
Wagner, Cs; Park, Hw; Leydesdorff, L	the continuing growth of global cooperation networks in research: a conundrum for national governments	2015
Park, Hw; Yoon, J; Leydesdorff, L	the normalization of co-authorship networks in the bibliometric evaluation: the government stimulation programs of china and korea	2016
Velez-Cuartas, G; Lucio-Arias, D; Leydesdorff, L	regional and global science: publications from latin america and the caribbean in the scielo citation index and the web of science	2016
Wagner, Cs; Whetsell, Ta; Leydesdorff, L	growth of international collaboration in science: revisiting six specialties	2017
Leydesdorff, L; Bornmann, L; Wagner, Cs	the relative influences of government funding and international collaboration on citation impact	2019

Direct citation network (HistCite)

Fig. 29 Direct citation network of Top 50 high cited papers

Nodes: 50, Links: 192; LCS, top 50; Min: 12, Max: 45 (LCS scaled)

Table 9 Detailed information of publications in the direct citation network

No.	Nodes number	Publications	LCS	GCS
1.	5	LEYDESDORFF L, 1986, SCIENTOMETRICS, V9, P103	37	64
2.	7	LEYDESDORFF L, 1987, SCIENTOMETRICS, V11, P295	16	84
3.	13	AMSTERDAMSKA O, 1989, SCIENTOMETRICS, V15, P449	13	56
4.	16	LEYDESDORFF L, 1989, RES POLICY, V18, P209	35	107
5.	18	LEYDESDORFF L, 1990, SCI TECHNOL HUM VAL, V15, P305	19	71
6.	24	LEYDESDORFF L, 1991, SOC NETWORKS, V13, P301	28	44
7.	31	LEYDESDORFF L, 1993, SCIENTOMETRICS, V26, P135	14	55
8.	32	LEYDESDORFF L, 1993, J THEOR SOC BEHAV, V23, P47	17	26
9.	35	LEYDESDORFF L, 1994, RES POLICY, V23, P217	26	62
10.	47	Leydesdorff L, 1997, SCIENTOMETRICS, V38, P155	19	35
11.	49	Leydesdorff L, 1997, J AM SOC INFORM SCI, V48, P418	17	103
12.	53	Leydesdorff L, 1998, SCIENTOMETRICS, V43, P5	13	177
13.	57	Etzkowitz H, 2000, RES POLICY, V29, P109	37	2380
14.	59	Leydesdorff L, 2000, SCIENTOMETRICS, V47, P265	12	27
15.	60	Frenken K, 2000, RES POLICY, V29, P331	13	45
16.	71	Leydesdorff L, 2002, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V53, P987	12	23
17.	79	Leydesdorff L, 2003, SCIENTOMETRICS, V58, P445	18	100
18.	82	Leydesdorff L, 2004, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V55, P991	13	65
19.	88	Leydesdorff L, 2005, SCI COMMUN, V27, P64	12	57
20.	91	Park HW, 2005, SCIENTOMETRICS, V65, P3	15	77
21.	93	Leydesdorff L, 2005, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V56, P1469	13	24
22.	94	Wagner CS, 2005, RES POLICY, V34, P1608	18	436
23.	97	Zhou P, 2006, RES POLICY, V35, P83	19	311
24.	98	Leydesdorff L, 2006, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V57, P601	37	103
25.	99	Leydesdorff L, 2006, RES POLICY, V35, P181	21	92
26.	101	Leydesdorff L, 2006, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V57, P1470	14	36
27.	102	Leydesdorff L, 2006, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V57, P1616	15	201
28.	106	Leydesdorff L, 2006, RES POLICY, V35, P1538	23	95
29.	115	Leydesdorff L, 2007, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V58, P1303	14	222
30.	122	Leydesdorff L, 2008, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V59, P278	34	150
31.	127	Leydesdorff L, 2008, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V59, P1810	21	71
32.	136	Leydesdorff L, 2009, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V60, P348	19	303
33.	138	Leydesdorff L, 2009, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V60, P778	20	80
34.	140	Bensman SJ, 2009, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V60, P1097	16	40
35.	144	Rafols I, 2009, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V60, P1823	45	110
36.	161	Opthof T, 2010, J INFORMETR, V4, P423	24	117
37.	163	Leydesdorff L, 2010, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V61, P1622	15	65
38.	164	Rafols I, 2010, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V61, P1871	28	207
39.	168	Leydesdorff L, 2010, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V61, P2138	15	30
40.	172	Lengyel B, 2011, REG STUD, V45, P677	16	56
41.	174	Leydesdorff L, 2011, J INFORMETR, V5, P87	13	105
42.	177	Leydesdorff L, 2011, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V62, P217	13	80
43.	179	Leydesdorff L, 2011, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V62, P846	20	49
44.	183	Leydesdorff L, 2011, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V62, P1370	30	119
45.	189	Bornmann L, 2011, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V62, P1954	15	47
46.	190	Leydesdorff L, 2011, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V62, P2133	18	91
47.	198	Leydesdorff L, 2012, J INFORMETR, V6, P318	13	53
48.	199	Bornmann L, 2012, J INFORMETR, V6, P333	13	95
49.	206	Rafols I, 2012, RES POLICY, V41, P1262	19	204
50.	217	Bornmann L, 2013, J INFORMETR, V7, P158	13	81

▪ **Cited articles analysis**

RPYS analysis

Fig. 30 Reference Publication Year Spectroscopy (RPYS) analysis of the cited references

Authors co-citation analysis

Fig. 32 Reference co-citation analysis of Loet Leydesdorff

References co-citation analysis (CiteSpace)

Fig. 33 Reference co-citation clusters of Loet Leydesdorff

Fig. 34 Reference co-citation clusters of Loet Leydesdorff

Fig. 35 Top 5 high cited references in each cluster

Fig. 36 Timeline Visualization of the reference's co-citation analysis

Top 25 References with the Strongest Citation Bursts

Fig. 37 Top 25 References with the strongest citation bursts

- **Scientometric mapping tools**
- **CiteSpace**
<https://sourceforge.net/projects/citespace/files/latest/download>
- **VOSviewer**
<https://www.vosviewer.com/>
- **CitNetExplorer**
<https://www.citnetexplorer.nl/>
- **NetsCity**
http://37.187.79.5/netscitypg/importer_fichier_1_choice.php?lang=en
- **leydesdorff.net**
<https://www.leydesdorff.net/overlaytoolkit/index.htm>
- **HistCite**

▪ Appendix

First Author papers of Loet Leydesdorff [1-201], other papers [202-338].

Reference

- [1] L. Leydesdorff, THE DUTCH SCIENCE SHOPS, Trends in Biochemical Sciences, 5 (1980) R1-R2.
- [2] L. Leydesdorff, THE STRATEGIC ADJUSTMENT OF TECHNOLOGICAL POSSIBILITIES TO SOCIAL PRIORITIES, Bulletin of Science Technology & Society, 2 (1982) 525-533.
- [3] L. Leydesdorff, THE DEVELOPMENT OF FRAMES OF REFERENCES, Scientometrics, 9 (1986) 103-125.
- [4] L. Leydesdorff, TOWARDS A THEORY OF CITATION, Scientometrics, 12 (1987) 305-309.
- [5] L. Leydesdorff, VARIOUS METHODS FOR THE MAPPING OF SCIENCE, Scientometrics, 11 (1987) 295-324.
- [6] L. Leydesdorff, WORDS AND CO-WORDS AS INDICATORS OF INTELLECTUAL ORGANIZATION, Research Policy, 18 (1989) 209-223.
- [7] L. Leydesdorff, THE SCIENCE CITATION INDEX AND THE MEASUREMENT OF NATIONAL PERFORMANCE IN TERMS OF NUMBERS OF SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS, Scientometrics, 17 (1989) 111-120.
- [8] L. Leydesdorff, THE RELATIONS BETWEEN QUALITATIVE THEORY AND SCIENTOMETRIC METHODS IN SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY STUDIES - INTRODUCTION TO THE TOPICAL ISSUE, Scientometrics, 15 (1989) 333-347.
- [9] L. Leydesdorff, RELATIONS AMONG SCIENCE INDICATORS OR MORE GENERALLY AMONG ANYTHING ONE MIGHT WISH TO COUNT ABOUT TEXTS, Scientometrics, 19 (1990) 271-296.
- [10] L. Leydesdorff, THE PREDICTION OF SCIENCE INDICATORS USING INFORMATION-THEORY, Scientometrics, 19 (1990) 297-324.
- [11] L. Leydesdorff, RELATIONS AMONG SCIENCE INDICATORS OR MORE GENERALLY AMONG ANYTHING ONE MIGHT WISH TO COUNT ABOUT TEXTS .1. THE STATIC MODEL, Scientometrics, 18 (1990) 281-307.
- [12] L. Leydesdorff, THE STATIC AND DYNAMIC ANALYSIS OF NETWORK DATA USING INFORMATION-THEORY, Social Networks, 13 (1991) 301-345.
- [13] L. Leydesdorff, ON THE SCIENTOMETRIC DECLINE OF BRITISH SCIENCE - ONE ADDITIONAL GRAPH IN REPLY TO MARTIN,BEN, Scientometrics, 20 (1991) 363-367.
- [14] L. Leydesdorff, IN SEARCH OF EPISTEMIC NETWORKS, Social Studies of Science, 21 (1991) 75-110.
- [15] L. Leydesdorff, A VALIDATION-STUDY OF LEXIMAPPE, Scientometrics, 25 (1992) 295-312.
- [16] L. Leydesdorff, A VALIDATION-STUDY OF LEXIMAPPE - REPLY, Scientometrics, 25 (1992) 317-319.
- [17] L. Leydesdorff, IRREVERSIBILITIES IN SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY NETWORKS - AN EMPIRICAL AND ANALYTICAL APPROACH, Scientometrics, 24 (1992) 321-357.
- [18] L. Leydesdorff, KNOWLEDGE REPRESENTATIONS, BAYESIAN INFERENCES AND EMPIRICAL SCIENCE STUDIES, Social Science Information Sur Les Sciences Sociales, 31 (1992) 213-237.
- [19] L. Leydesdorff, THE SCIENCE OF SOCIETAL MATTERS - GERMAN - LUHMANN,N, Sci. Technol. Hum. Values, 17 (1992) 248-253.
- [20] L. Leydesdorff, STRUCTURE ACTION CONTINGENCIES AND THE MODEL OF PARALLEL DISTRIBUTED-PROCESSING, Journal for the Theory of Social Behaviour, 23 (1993) 47-77.
- [21] L. Leydesdorff, IS SOCIETY A SELF-ORGANIZING SYSTEM, Journal of Social and Evolutionary Systems, 16 (1993) 331-349.
- [22] L. Leydesdorff, THE GENERATION OF AGGREGATED JOURNAL-JOURNAL CITATION MAPS ON THE BASIS OF THE CD-ROM VERSION OF THE SCIENCE-CITATION-INDEX, Scientometrics, 31 (1994) 59-84.
- [23] L. Leydesdorff, SCIENTOMETRICS - FRENCH - CALLON,M, COURTIAL,JP, PENAN,H, Scientometrics, 30 (1994) 539-541.
- [24] L. Leydesdorff, UNCERTAINTY AND THE COMMUNICATION OF TIME, Systems Research, 11 (1994) 31-51.
- [25] L. Leydesdorff, THE EVOLUTION OF COMMUNICATION-SYSTEMS, Systems Research and Information Science, 6 (1994) 219-230.
- [26] L. Leydesdorff, THE OPERATION OF THE SOCIAL SYSTEM IN A MODEL-BASED ON CELLULAR-AUTOMATA, Social Science Information Sur Les Sciences Sociales, 34 (1995) 413-441.
- [27] L. Leydesdorff, The production of probabilistic entropy in structure action contingency relations,

- Journal of Social and Evolutionary Systems, 18 (1995) 339-356.
- [28] L. Leydesdorff, Luhmann's sociological theory: Its operationalization and future perspectives, *Social Science Information Sur Les Sciences Sociales*, 35 (1996) 283-306.
- [29] L. Leydesdorff, Sustainable technological developments and second-order cybernetics, *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*, 9 (1997) 329-341.
- [30] L. Leydesdorff, Why words and co-words cannot map the development of the sciences, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science*, 48 (1997) 418-427.
- [31] L. Leydesdorff, The non-linear dynamics of sociological reflections, *International Sociology*, 12 (1997) 25-45.
- [32] L. Leydesdorff, Theories of citation?, *Scientometrics*, 43 (1998) 5-25.
- [33] L. Leydesdorff, Reply about using co-words, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science*, 49 (1998) 98-99.
- [34] L. Leydesdorff, Luhmann, Habermas and the theory of communication, *Systems Research and Behavioral Science*, 17 (2000) 273-288.
- [35] L. Leydesdorff, The triple helix: an evolutionary model of innovations, *Research Policy*, 29 (2000) 243-255.
- [36] L. Leydesdorff, Is the European Union becoming a single publication system?, *Scientometrics*, 47 (2000) 265-280.
- [37] L. Leydesdorff, The cybrarian's manual 2, *Journal of Documentation*, 57 (2001) 824-826.
- [38] L. Leydesdorff, Technology and culture: The dissemination and the potential 'lock-in' of new technologies, *Jasss-the Journal of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation*, 4 (2001) U20-U44.
- [39] L. Leydesdorff, The complex dynamics of technological innovation: A comparison of models using cellular automata, *Systems Research and Behavioral Science*, 19 (2002) 563-575.
- [40] L. Leydesdorff, Dynamic and evolutionary updates of classificatory schemes in scientific journal structures, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 53 (2002) 987-994.
- [41] L. Leydesdorff, The communication turn in the theory of social systems, *Systems Research and Behavioral Science*, 19 (2002) 129-136.
- [42] L. Leydesdorff, Indicators of structural change in the dynamics of science: Entropy statistics of the SCI Journal Citation Reports, *Scientometrics*, 53 (2002) 131-159.
- [43] L. Leydesdorff, The mutual information of university-industry-government relations: An indicator of the Triple Helix dynamics, *Scientometrics*, 58 (2003) 445-467.
- [44] L. Leydesdorff, Rejoinder to Van den Besselaar's letter entitled "descriptive statistics, inferential statistics, rhetorical statistics", *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 54 (2003) 1077-1078.
- [45] L. Leydesdorff, Empirical evidence of self-organization? A rejoinder, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 54 (2003) 804-804.
- [46] L. Leydesdorff, A methodological perspective on the evaluation of the promotion of university-industry-government relations, *Small Business Economics*, 20 (2003) 201-204.
- [47] L. Leydesdorff, Can networks of journal-journal citations be used as indicators of change in the social sciences?, *Journal of Documentation*, 59 (2003) 84-104.
- [48] L. Leydesdorff, The university-industry knowledge relationship: Analyzing patents and the science base of technologies, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 55 (2004) 991-1001.
- [49] L. Leydesdorff, Clusters and maps of science journals based on bi-connected graphs in Journal Citation Reports, *Journal of Documentation*, 60 (2004) 371-427.
- [50] L. Leydesdorff, Top-down decomposition of the Journal Citation Report of the Social Science Citation Index: Graph- and factor-analytical approaches, *Scientometrics*, 60 (2004) 159-180.
- [51] L. Leydesdorff, Evaluation of research and evolution of science indicators, *Curr. Sci.*, 89 (2005) 1510-1517.
- [52] L. Leydesdorff, Similarity measures, author cocitation analysis, and information theory, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 56 (2005) 769-772.
- [53] L. Leydesdorff, The scientific impact of China, *Scientometrics*, 63 (2005) 411-412.
- [54] L. Leydesdorff, Anticipatory systems and the processing of meaning: a simulation study inspired by Luhmann's theory of social systems, *Jasss-the Journal of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation*, 8 (2005).

- [55] L. Leydesdorff, Can scientific journals be classified in terms of aggregated journal-journal citation relations using the Journal Citation Reports?, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 57 (2006) 601-613.
- [56] L. Leydesdorff, The biological metaphor of a second-order observer and the sociological discourse, *Kybernetes*, 35 (2006) 531-546.
- [57] L. Leydesdorff, Should co-occurrence data be normalized? A rejoinder, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 58 (2007) 2411-2413.
- [58] L. Leydesdorff, Include citations when ranking institutions and scholars, *Communications of the Acm*, 50 (2007) 14-14.
- [59] L. Leydesdorff, Environment and Planning B: Planning and Design as a journal: The interdisciplinarity of its environment and the citation impact, *Environment and Planning B-Planning & Design*, 34 (2007) 826-838.
- [60] L. Leydesdorff, Betweenness centrality as an indicator of the interdisciplinarity of scientific journals, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 58 (2007) 1303-1319.
- [61] L. Leydesdorff, Mapping interdisciplinarity at the interfaces between the science citation index and the social science citation index, *Scientometrics*, 71 (2007) 391-405.
- [62] L. Leydesdorff, Visualization of the citation impact environments of scientific journals: An online mapping exercise, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 58 (2007) 25-38.
- [63] L. Leydesdorff, Configurational Information as Potentially Negative Entropy: The Triple Helix Model, *Entropy*, 10 (2008) 391-410.
- [64] L. Leydesdorff, Patent classifications as indicators of intellectual organization, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 59 (2008) 1582-1597.
- [65] L. Leydesdorff, The delineation of nanoscience and nanotechnology in terms of journals and patents: A most recent update, *Scientometrics*, 76 (2008) 159-167.
- [66] L. Leydesdorff, Caveats for the use of citation indicators in research and journal evaluations, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 59 (2008) 278-287.
- [67] L. Leydesdorff, On the normalization and visualization of author co-citation data: Salton's cosine versus the Jaccard index, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 59 (2008) 77-85.
- [68] L. Leydesdorff, How are New Citation-Based Journal Indicators Adding to the Bibliometric Toolbox?, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 60 (2009) 1327-1336.
- [69] L. Leydesdorff, The non-linear dynamics of meaning processing in social systems, *Social Science Information Sur Les Sciences Sociales*, 48 (2009) 5-33.
- [70] L. Leydesdorff, Interaction information: linear and nonlinear interpretations, *International Journal of General Systems*, 38 (2009) 681-685.
- [71] L. Leydesdorff, The Communication of Meaning and the Structuration of Expectations: Giddens' "Structuration Theory" and Luhmann's "Self-Organization", *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 61 (2010) 2138-2150.
- [72] L. Leydesdorff, The Knowledge-Based Economy and the Triple Helix Model, *Annual Review of Information Science and Technology*, 44 (2010) 367-417.
- [73] L. Leydesdorff, Redundancy in Systems Which Entertain a Model of Themselves: Interaction Information and the Self-Organization of Anticipation, *Entropy*, 12 (2010) 63-79.
- [74] L. Leydesdorff, 'Meaning' as a sociological concept: A review of the modeling, mapping and simulation of the communication of knowledge and meaning, *Social Science Information Sur Les Sciences Sociales*, 50 (2011) 391-413.
- [75] L. Leydesdorff, "Structuration" by intellectual organization: the configuration of knowledge in relations among structural components in networks of science, *Scientometrics*, 88 (2011) 499-520.
- [76] L. Leydesdorff, Atlas of science: visualizing what we know, *Scientometrics*, 88 (2011) 675-677.
- [77] L. Leydesdorff, Ignorance and Surprise: Science, Society, and Ecological Design, *American Journal of Sociology*, 116 (2011) 2022-2024.
- [78] L. Leydesdorff, Accounting for the uncertainty in the evaluation of percentile ranks, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 63 (2012) 2349-2350.
- [79] L. Leydesdorff, McCall's area transformation versus the integrated impact indicator (I3), *Journal of*

Informetrics, 6 (2012) 513-514.

- [80] L. Leydesdorff, Alternatives to the journal impact factor: I_3 and the top-10% (or top-25%?) of the most highly cited papers, *Scientometrics*, 92 (2012) 355-365.
- [81] L. Leydesdorff, WORLD SHARES OF PUBLICATIONS OF THE USA, EU-27, AND CHINA COMPARED AND PREDICTED USING THE NEW WEB OF SCIENCE INTERFACE VERSUS SCOPUS, *Prof. Inf.*, 21 (2012) 43-49.
- [82] L. Leydesdorff, Sociological and Communication-Theoretical Perspectives on the Commercialization of the Sciences, *Science & Education*, 22 (2013) 2511-2527.
- [83] L. Leydesdorff, Statistics for the dynamic analysis of scientometric data: the evolution of the sciences in terms of trajectories and regimes, *Scientometrics*, 96 (2013) 731-741.
- [84] L. Leydesdorff, The revised SNIP indicator of Elsevier's Scopus, *Journal of Informetrics*, 7 (2013) 859-860.
- [85] L. Leydesdorff, Does the specification of uncertainty hurt the progress of scientometrics?, *Journal of Informetrics*, 7 (2013) 292-293.
- [86] L. Leydesdorff, An evaluation of impacts in "Nanoscience & nanotechnology": steps towards standards for citation analysis, *Scientometrics*, 94 (2013) 35-55.
- [87] L. Leydesdorff, Can technology life-cycles be indicated by diversity in patent classifications? The crucial role of variety, *Scientometrics*, 105 (2015) 1441-1451.
- [88] L. Leydesdorff, Can intellectual processes in the sciences also be simulated? The anticipation and visualization of possible future states, *Scientometrics*, 105 (2015) 2197-2214.
- [89] L. Leydesdorff, The positive side of discursive disagreements in the social sciences, *Journal of Informetrics*, 11 (2017) 1043-1043.
- [90] L. Leydesdorff, Bibliometrics and Research Evaluation: Uses and Abuses, *Journal of Informetrics*, 11 (2017) 595-597.
- [91] L. Leydesdorff, Diversity and interdisciplinarity: how can one distinguish and recombine disparity, variety, and balance?, *Scientometrics*, 116 (2018) 2113-2121.
- [92] L. Leydesdorff, Lifting the Markov blankets of socio-cultural evolution A comment on "Answering Schrodinger's question: A free-energy formulation" by Maxwell James Desormeau Ramstead et al, *Physics of Life Reviews*, 24 (2018) 45-46.
- [93] L. Leydesdorff, P. Ahrweiler, In Search of a Network Theory of Innovations: Relations, Positions, and Perspectives, *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 65 (2014) 2359-2374.
- [94] L. Leydesdorff, F. Alkemade, G. Heimeriks, R. Hoekstra, Patents as instruments for exploring innovation dynamics: geographic and technological perspectives on "photovoltaic cells", *Scientometrics*, 102 (2015) 629-651.
- [95] L. Leydesdorff, O. Amsterdamska, DIMENSIONS OF CITATION ANALYSIS, *Sci. Technol. Hum. Values*, 15 (1990) 305-335.
- [96] L. Leydesdorff, S. Bensman, Classification and powerlaws: The logarithmic transformation, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 57 (2006) 1470-1486.
- [97] L. Leydesdorff, L. Bornmann, Integrated Impact Indicators Compared With Impact Factors: An Alternative Research Design With Policy Implications, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 62 (2011) 2133-2146.
- [98] L. Leydesdorff, L. Bornmann, How Fractional Counting of Citations Affects the Impact Factor: Normalization in Terms of Differences in Citation Potentials Among Fields of Science, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 62 (2011) 217-229.
- [99] L. Leydesdorff, L. Bornmann, Percentile ranks and the integrated impact indicator (I_3), *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 63 (2012) 1901-1902.
- [100] L. Leydesdorff, L. Bornmann, Testing differences statistically with the Leiden ranking, *Scientometrics*, 92 (2012) 781-783.
- [101] L. Leydesdorff, L. Bornmann, Mapping (USPTO) Patent Data Using Overlays to Google Maps, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 63 (2012) 1442-1458.
- [102] L. Leydesdorff, L. Bornmann, The operationalization of "fields" as WoS subject categories (WCs) in evaluative bibliometrics: The cases of "library and information science" and "science & technology studies", *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 67 (2016) 707-714.
- [103] L. Leydesdorff, L. Bornmann, J. Adams, The integrated impact indicator revisited(I_3^*): a non-parametric alternative to the journal impact factor, *Scientometrics*, 119 (2019) 1669-1694.

- [104] L. Leydesdorff, L. Bornmann, W. Marx, S. Milojevic, Referenced Publication Years Spectroscopy applied to iMetrics: Scientometrics, Journal of Informetrics, and a relevant subset of JASIST, Journal of Informetrics, 8 (2014) 162-174.
- [105] L. Leydesdorff, L. Bornmann, J. Mingers, Statistical significance and effect sizes of differences among research universities at the level of nations and worldwide based on the leiden rankings, Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology, 70 (2019) 509-525.
- [106] L. Leydesdorff, L. Bornmann, R. Mutz, T. Opthof, Turning the Tables on Citation Analysis One More Time: Principles for Comparing Sets of Documents, Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology, 62 (2011) 1370-1381.
- [107] L. Leydesdorff, L. Bornmann, T. Opthof, h: the scientist as chimpanzee or bonobo, Scientometrics, 118 (2019) 1163-1166.
- [108] L. Leydesdorff, L. Bornmann, C.S. Wagner, Generating clustered journal maps: an automated system for hierarchical classification, Scientometrics, 110 (2017) 1601-1614.
- [109] L. Leydesdorff, L. Bornmann, C.S. Wagner, The Relative Influences of Government Funding and International Collaboration on Citation Impact, Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology, 70 (2019) 198-201.
- [110] L. Leydesdorff, L. Bornmann, P. Zhou, Construction of a pragmatic base line for journal classifications and maps based on aggregated journal-journal citation relations, Journal of Informetrics, 10 (2016) 902-918.
- [111] L. Leydesdorff, S. Carley, I. Rafols, Global maps of science based on the new Web-of-Science categories, Scientometrics, 94 (2013) 589-593.
- [112] L. Leydesdorff, J.A. Comins, A.A. Sorensen, L. Bornmann, I. Hellsten, Cited references and Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) as two different knowledge representations: clustering and mappings at the paper level, Scientometrics, 109 (2016) 2077-2091.
- [113] L. Leydesdorff, S. Cozzens, P. Vandenbesselaar, TRACKING AREAS OF STRATEGIC IMPORTANCE USING SCIENTOMETRIC JOURNAL MAPPINGS, Research Policy, 23 (1994) 217-229.
- [114] L. Leydesdorff, S.E. Cozzens, THE DELINEATION OF SPECIALITIES IN TERMS OF JOURNALS USING THE DYNAMIC JOURNAL SET OF THE SCI, Scientometrics, 26 (1993) 135-156.
- [115] L. Leydesdorff, I. Cucco, Regions, innovation systems, and the North-South divide in Italy, Prof. Inf., 28 (2019).
- [116] L. Leydesdorff, R. de Klerk, An innovative introductory course at the University of Amsterdam, International Journal of Science Education, 20 (1998) 15-23.
- [117] L. Leydesdorff, F. de Moya-Anegon, W. de Nooy, Aggregated journal-journal citation relations in scopus and web of science matched and compared in terms of networks, maps, and interactive overlays, Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology, 67 (2016) 2194-2211.
- [118] L. Leydesdorff, F. de Moya-Anegon, V.P. Guerrero-Bote, Journal Maps on the Basis of Scopus Data: A Comparison with the Journal Citation Reports of the ISI, Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology, 61 (2010) 352-369.
- [119] L. Leydesdorff, F. de Moya-Anegon, V.P. Guerrero-Bote, Journal Maps, Interactive Overlays, and the Measurement of Interdisciplinarity on the Basis of Scopus Data (1996-2012), Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology, 66 (2015) 1001-1016.
- [120] L. Leydesdorff, W. de Nooy, Can "Hot Spots" in the Sciences Be Mapped Using the Dynamics of Aggregated Journal-Journal Citation Relations?, Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology, 68 (2017) 197-213.
- [121] L. Leydesdorff, M. Deakin, The Triple-Helix Model of Smart Cities: A Neo-Evolutionary Perspective, Journal of Urban Technology, 18 (2011) 53-63.
- [122] L. Leydesdorff, W. Dolfsma, G. Van der Panne, Measuring the knowledge base of an economy in terms of triple-helix relations among 'technology, organization, and territory', Research Policy, 35 (2006) 181-199.
- [123] L. Leydesdorff, S. Franse, The Communication of Meaning in Social Systems, Systems Research and Behavioral Science, 26 (2009) 109-117.
- [124] L. Leydesdorff, M. Fritsch, Measuring the knowledge base of regional innovation systems in Germany in terms of a Triple Helix dynamics, Research Policy, 35 (2006) 1538-1553.
- [125] L. Leydesdorff, L. Gauthier, The evaluation of national performance in selected priority areas using scientometric methods, Research Policy, 25 (1996) 431-450.
- [126] L. Leydesdorff, R.L. Goldstone, Interdisciplinarity at the Journal and Specialty Level: The Changing

Knowledge Bases of the Journal Cognitive Science, Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology, 65 (2014) 164-177.

[127] L. Leydesdorff, B. Hammarfelt, A. Salah, The Structure of the Arts & Humanities Citation Index: A Mapping on the Basis of Aggregated Citations Among 1,157 Journals, Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology, 62 (2011) 2414-2426.

[128] L. Leydesdorff, G. Heimeriks, The self-organization of the European information society: The case of "biotechnology", Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology, 52 (2001) 1262-1274.

[129] L. Leydesdorff, G. Heimeriks, D. Rotolo, Journal portfolio analysis for countries, cities, and organizations: Maps and comparisons, Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology, 67 (2016) 741-748.

[130] L. Leydesdorff, I. Hellsten, Metaphors and diaphors in science communication, Science Communication, 27 (2005) 64-99.

[131] L. Leydesdorff, I. Hellsten, Measuring the meaning of words in contexts: An automated analysis of controversies about 'Monarch butterflies,' 'Frankenfoods,' and 'stem cells', Scientometrics, 67 (2006) 231-258.

[132] L. Leydesdorff, I.A. Ivanova, Mutual Redundancies in Interhuman Communication Systems: Steps Toward a Calculus of Processing Meaning, Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology, 65 (2014) 386-399.

[133] L. Leydesdorff, B.H. Jin, Mapping the Chinese Science Citation Database in terms of aggregated journal-journal citation relations, Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology, 56 (2005) 1469-1479.

[134] L. Leydesdorff, M.W. Johnson, I. Ivanova, Toward a calculus of redundancy: Signification, codification, and anticipation in cultural evolution, Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology, 69 (2018) 1181-1192.

[135] L. Leydesdorff, M.W. Johnson, I.A. Ivanova, The communication of expectations and individual understanding Redundancy as reduction of uncertainty, and the processing of meaning, Kybernetes, 43 (2014) 1362-1371.

[136] L. Leydesdorff, G.F. Khan, L. Bornmann, THE GENERATION OF LARGE NETWORKS FROM WEB OF SCIENCE DATA, Prof. Inf., 23 (2014) 589-593.

[137] L. Leydesdorff, D.F. Kogler, B.W. Yan, Mapping patent classifications: portfolio and statistical analysis, and the comparison of strengths and weaknesses, Scientometrics, 112 (2017) 1573-1591.

[138] L. Leydesdorff, D. Kushnir, I. Rafols, Interactive overlay maps for US patent (USPTO) data based on International Patent Classification (IPC), Scientometrics, 98 (2014) 1583-1599.

[139] L. Leydesdorff, M. Meyer, The Triple Helix of university-industry-government relations, Scientometrics, 58 (2003) 191-203.

[140] L. Leydesdorff, M. Meyer, Triple Helix indicators of knowledge-based innovation systems - Introduction to the special issue, Research Policy, 35 (2006) 1441-1449.

[141] L. Leydesdorff, M. Meyer, The scientometrics of a Triple Helix of university-industry-government relations - (Introduction to the topical issue), Scientometrics, 70 (2007) 207-222.

[142] L. Leydesdorff, M. Meyer, The decline of university patenting and the end of the Bayh-Dole effect, Scientometrics, 83 (2010) 355-362.

[143] L. Leydesdorff, M. Meyer, A reply to Etzkowitz' comments to Leydesdorff and Martin (2010): technology transfer and the end of the Bayh-Dole effect, Scientometrics, 97 (2013) 927-934.

[144] L. Leydesdorff, S. Milojevic, The Citation Impact of German Sociology Journals: Some Problems with the Use of Scientometric Indicators in Journal and Research Evaluations, Soziale Welt-Zeitschrift Fur Sozialwissenschaftliche Forschung Und Praxis, 66 (2015) 193-204.

[145] L. Leydesdorff, A. Nerghe, Co-word Maps and Topic Modeling: A Comparison Using Small and Medium-Sized Corpora ($N < 1,000$), Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology, 68 (2017) 1024-1035.

[146] L. Leydesdorff, N.A. Oomes, Is the European Monetary System converging to integration?, Social Science Information Sur Les Sciences Sociales, 38 (1999) 57-86.

[147] L. Leydesdorff, T. Opthof, Scopus's Source Normalized Impact per Paper (SNIP) Versus a Journal Impact Factor Based on Fractional Counting of Citations, Journal of the American Society for Information

Science and Technology, 61 (2010) 2365-2369.

- [148] L. Leydesdorff, T. Opthof, Normalization at the field level: Fractional counting of citations, *Journal of Informetrics*, 4 (2010) 644-646.
- [149] L. Leydesdorff, T. Opthof, Scopus' SNIP Indicator: Reply to Moed, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 62 (2011) 214-215.
- [150] L. Leydesdorff, T. Opthof, Remaining problems with the "New Crown Indicator" (MNCS) of the CWTS, *Journal of Informetrics*, 5 (2011) 224-225.
- [151] L. Leydesdorff, T. Opthof, A rejoinder on energy versus impact indicators, *Scientometrics*, 90 (2012) 745-748.
- [152] L. Leydesdorff, T. Opthof, Citation analysis with medical subject Headings (MeSH) using the Web of Knowledge: A new routine, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 64 (2013) 1076-1080.
- [153] L. Leydesdorff, H.W. Park, Full and fractional counting in bibliometric networks, *Journal of Informetrics*, 11 (2017) 117-120.
- [154] L. Leydesdorff, H.W. Park, B. Lengyel, A routine for measuring synergy in university-industry-government relations: mutual information as a Triple-Helix and Quadruple-Helix indicator, *Scientometrics*, 99 (2014) 27-35.
- [155] L. Leydesdorff, H.W. Park, C. Wagner, International Coauthorship Relations in the Social Sciences Citation Index: Is Internationalization Leading the Network?, *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 65 (2014) 2111-2126.
- [156] L. Leydesdorff, E. Perevodchikov, A. Uvarov, Measuring triple-helix synergy in the Russian innovation systems at regional, provincial, and national levels, *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 66 (2015) 1229-1238.
- [157] L. Leydesdorff, O. Persson, Mapping the Geography of Science: Distribution Patterns and Networks of Relations Among Cities and Institutes, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 61 (2010) 1622-1634.
- [158] L. Leydesdorff, A.M. Petersen, I. Ivanova, Self-organization of meaning and the reflexive communication of information, *Social Science Information Sur Les Sciences Sociales*, 56 (2017) 4-27.
- [159] L. Leydesdorff, I. Porto-Gomez, Measuring the expected synergy in Spanish regional and national systems of innovation, *Journal of Technology Transfer*, 44 (2019) 189-209.
- [160] L. Leydesdorff, C. Probst, The Delineation of an Interdisciplinary Specialty in Terms of a Journal Set: The Case of Communication Studies, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 60 (2009) 1709-1718.
- [161] L. Leydesdorff, F. Radicchi, L. Bornmann, C. Castellano, W. de Nooy, Field-Normalized Impact Factors (IFs): A Comparison of Rescaling and Fractionally Counted IFs, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 64 (2013) 2299-2309.
- [162] L. Leydesdorff, I. Rafols, A Global Map of Science Based on the ISI Subject Categories, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 60 (2009) 348-362.
- [163] L. Leydesdorff, I. Rafols, Local Emergence and Global Diffusion of Research Technologies: An Exploration of Patterns of Network Formation, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 62 (2011) 846-860.
- [164] L. Leydesdorff, I. Rafols, Indicators of the interdisciplinarity of journals: Diversity, centrality, and citations, *Journal of Informetrics*, 5 (2011) 87-100.
- [165] L. Leydesdorff, I. Rafols, Interactive overlays: A new method for generating global journal maps from Web-of-Science data, *Journal of Informetrics*, 6 (2012) 318-332.
- [166] L. Leydesdorff, I. Rafols, C.M. Chen, Interactive Overlays of Journals and the Measurement of Interdisciplinarity on the Basis of Aggregated Journal-Journal Citations, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 64 (2013) 2573-2586.
- [167] L. Leydesdorff, D. Rotolo, W. de Nooy, Innovation as a nonlinear process, the scientometric perspective, and the specification of an "innovation opportunities explorer", *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*, 25 (2013) 641-653.
- [168] L. Leydesdorff, D. Rotolo, I. Rafols, Bibliometric perspectives on medical innovation using the medical subject Headings of PubMed, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 63 (2012) 2239-2253.

- [169] L. Leydesdorff, A.A.A. Salah, Maps on the Basis of the Arts & Humanities Citation Index: The Journals Leonardo and Art Journal Versus "Digital Humanities" as a Topic, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 61 (2010) 787-801.
- [170] L. Leydesdorff, T. Schank, Dynamic animations of journal maps: Indicators of structural changes and interdisciplinary developments, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 59 (2008) 1810-1818.
- [171] L. Leydesdorff, T. Schank, A. Scharnhorst, W. de Nooy, Animating the development of Social networks over time using a dynamic extension of multidimensional scaling, *Prof. Inf.*, 17 (2008) 611-626.
- [172] L. Leydesdorff, J.C. Shin, How to Evaluate Universities in Terms of Their Relative Citation Impacts: Fractional Counting of Citations and the Normalization of Differences Among Disciplines, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 62 (2011) 1146-1155.
- [173] L. Leydesdorff, O. Strand, The Swedish System of Innovation: Regional Synergies in a Knowledge-Based Economy, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 64 (2013) 1890-1902.
- [174] L. Leydesdorff, Y. Sun, National and International Dimensions of the Triple Helix in Japan: University-Industry-Government Versus International Coauthorship Relations, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 60 (2009) 778-788.
- [175] L. Leydesdorff, A. Thor, L. Bornmann, FURTHER STEPS IN INTEGRATING THE PLATFORMS OF WoS AND SCOPUS: HISTORIOGRAPHY WITH HISTCITE (TM) AND MAIN-PATH ANALYSIS, *Prof. Inf.*, 26 (2017) 662-670.
- [176] L. Leydesdorff, P. Van den Besselaar, Scientometrics and communication theory: Towards theoretically informed indicators, *Scientometrics*, 38 (1997) 155-174.
- [177] L. Leydesdorff, P. Vandenbesselaar, SQUEEZED BETWEEN CAPITAL AND TECHNOLOGY - ON THE PARTICIPATION OF LABOR IN THE KNOWLEDGE SOCIETY, *Acta Sociologica*, 30 (1987) 339-353.
- [178] L. Leydesdorff, H. Vanerkelens, SOME SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF BECOMING A PHYSICIST, *Scientometrics*, 3 (1981) 27-45.
- [179] L. Leydesdorff, L. Vaughan, Co-occurrence matrices and their applications in information science: Extending ACA to the Web environment, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 57 (2006) 1616-1628.
- [180] L. Leydesdorff, C. Wagner, Macro-level indicators of the relations between research funding and research output, *Journal of Informetrics*, 3 (2009) 353-362.
- [181] L. Leydesdorff, C. Wagner, Is the United States losing ground in science? A global perspective on the world science system, *Scientometrics*, 78 (2009) 23-36.
- [182] L. Leydesdorff, C. Wagner, L. Bornmann, Replicability and the public/private divide, *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 67 (2016) 1777-1778.
- [183] L. Leydesdorff, C.S. Wagner, International collaboration in science and the formation of a core group, *Journal of Informetrics*, 2 (2008) 317-325.
- [184] L. Leydesdorff, C.S. Wagner, L. Bornmann, The European Union, China, and the United States in the top-1% and top-10% layers of most-frequently cited publications: Competition and collaborations, *Journal of Informetrics*, 8 (2014) 606-617.
- [185] L. Leydesdorff, C.S. Wagner, L. Bornmann, Discontinuities in citation relations among journals: self-organized criticality as a model of scientific revolutions and change, *Scientometrics*, 116 (2018) 623-644.
- [186] L. Leydesdorff, C.S. Wagner, L. Bornmann, Betweenness and diversity in journal citation networks as measures of interdisciplinarity-A tribute to Eugene Garfield, *Scientometrics*, 114 (2018) 567-592.
- [187] L. Leydesdorff, C.S. Wagner, L. Bornmann, Interdisciplinarity as diversity in citation patterns among journals: Rao-Stirling diversity, relative variety, and the Gini coefficient, *Journal of Informetrics*, 13 (2019) 255-269.
- [188] L. Leydesdorff, C.S. Wagner, H.W. Park, J. Adams, INTERNATIONAL COLLABORATION IN SCIENCE: THE GLOBAL MAP AND THE NETWORK, *Prof. Inf.*, 22 (2013) 87-94.
- [189] L. Leydesdorff, J. Ward, Science shops: a kaleidoscope of science-society collaborations in Europe, *Public Underst. Sci.*, 14 (2005) 353-372.
- [190] L. Leydesdorff, K. Welbers, The semantic mapping of words and co-words in contexts, *Journal of Informetrics*, 5 (2011) 469-475.
- [191] L. Leydesdorff, P. Wouters, CRISIS OR CRITIQUE, *Scientometrics*, 30 (1994) 433-437.

- [192] L. Leydesdorff, P. Wouters, Between texts and contexts: Advances in theories of citation? (a rejoinder), *Scientometrics*, 44 (1999) 169-182.
- [193] L. Leydesdorff, P. Wouters, L. Bornmann, Professional and citizen bibliometrics: complementarities and ambivalences in the development and use of indicators-a state-of-the-art report, *Scientometrics*, 109 (2016) 2129-2150.
- [194] L. Leydesdorff, G. Zawdie, The triple helix perspective of innovation systems, *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*, 22 (2010) 789-804.
- [195] L. Leydesdorff, S. Zeldenrust, TECHNOLOGICAL-CHANGE AND TRADE-UNIONS, *Research Policy*, 13 (1984) 153-164.
- [196] L. Leydesdorff, P. Zhou, Are the contributions of China and Korea upsetting the world system of science?, *Scientometrics*, 63 (2005) 617-630.
- [197] L. Leydesdorff, P. Zhou, Nanotechnology as a field of science: Its delineation in terms of journals and patents, *Scientometrics*, 70 (2007) 693-713.
- [198] L. Leydesdorff, P. Zhou, Co-word analysis using the Chinese character set, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 59 (2008) 1528-1530.
- [199] L. Leydesdorff, P. Zhou, Measuring the knowledge-based economy of China in terms of synergy among technological, organizational, and geographic attributes of firms, *Scientometrics*, 98 (2014) 1703-1719.
- [200] L. Leydesdorff, P. Zhou, L. Bornmann, How can journal impact factors be normalized across fields of science? An assessment in terms of percentile ranks and fractional counts, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 64 (2013) 96-107.
- [201] L. Leydesdorff, C.S. Wagner, I. Porto-Gomez, J.A. Comins, F. Phillips, Synergy in the knowledge base of US innovation systems at national, state, and regional levels: The contributions of high-tech manufacturing and knowledge-intensive services, *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 70 (2019) 1108-1123.
- [202] A. Abbasi, L. Hossain, L. Leydesdorff, Betweenness centrality as a driver of preferential attachment in the evolution of research collaboration networks, *Journal of Informetrics*, 6 (2012) 403-412.
- [203] J. Adams, K. Gurney, D. Hook, L. Leydesdorff, International collaboration clusters in Africa, *Scientometrics*, 98 (2014) 547-556.
- [204] O. Amsterdamska, L. Leydesdorff, CITATIONS - INDICATORS OF SIGNIFICANCE, *Scientometrics*, 15 (1989) 449-471.
- [205] R. Arencibia-Jorge, L. Leydesdorff, Z. Chinchilla-Rodriguez, R. Rousseau, S.W. Paris, Retrieval of very large numbers of items in the Web of Science: an exercise to develop accurate search strategies, *Prof. Inf.*, 18 (2009) 529-533.
- [206] J. Bauer, L. Leydesdorff, L. Bornmann, Highly cited papers in Library and Information Science (LIS): Authors, institutions, and network structures, *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 67 (2016) 3095-3100.
- [207] S.E. Baumgartner, L. Leydesdorff, Group-Based Trajectory Modeling (GBTM) of Citations in Scholarly Literature: Dynamic Qualities of "Transient" and "Sticky Knowledge Claims", *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 65 (2014) 797-811.
- [208] S.J. Bensman, L. Leydesdorff, Definition and Identification of Journals as Bibliographic and Subject Entities: Librarianship Versus ISI Journal Citation Reports Methods and Their Effect on Citation Measures, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 60 (2009) 1097-1117.
- [209] L. Bornmann, J. Adams, L. Leydesdorff, The negative effects of citing with a national orientation in terms of recognition: National and international citations in natural-sciences papers from Germany, the Netherlands, and the UK, *Journal of Informetrics*, 12 (2018) 931-949.
- [210] L. Bornmann, F.D. Anegon, L. Leydesdorff, Do Scientific Advancements Lean on the Shoulders of Giants? A Bibliometric Investigation of the Ortega Hypothesis, *PLoS One*, 5 (2010).
- [211] L. Bornmann, F.D. Anegon, L. Leydesdorff, The new Excellence Indicator in the World Report of the SCImago Institutions Rankings 2011, *Journal of Informetrics*, 6 (2012) 333-335.
- [212] L. Bornmann, R. Haunschild, L. Leydesdorff, Reference publication year spectroscopy (RPYS) of Eugene Garfield's publications, *Scientometrics*, 114 (2018) 439-448.
- [213] L. Bornmann, L. Leydesdorff, Which Cities Produce More Excellent Papers Than Can Be Expected? A New Mapping Approach, Using Google Maps, Based on Statistical Significance Testing, *Journal of the*

American Society for Information Science and Technology, 62 (2011) 1954-1962.

[214] L. Bornmann, L. Leydesdorff, Which are the best performing regions in information science in terms of highly cited papers? Some improvements of our previous mapping approaches, *Journal of Informetrics*, 6 (2012) 336-345.

[215] L. Bornmann, L. Leydesdorff, Statistical tests and research assessments: A comment on Schneider (2012), *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 64 (2013) 1306-1308.

[216] L. Bornmann, L. Leydesdorff, Macro-Indicators of Citation Impacts of Six Prolific Countries: InCites Data and the Statistical Significance of Trends, *PLoS One*, 8 (2013).

[217] L. Bornmann, L. Leydesdorff, The validation of (advanced) bibliometric indicators through peer assessments: A comparative study using data from InCites and F1000, *Journal of Informetrics*, 7 (2013) 286-291.

[218] L. Bornmann, L. Leydesdorff, Scientometrics in a changing research landscape, *Embo Reports*, 15 (2014) 1228-1232.

[219] L. Bornmann, L. Leydesdorff, On the meaningful and non-meaningful use of reference sets in bibliometrics, *Journal of Informetrics*, 8 (2014) 273-275.

[220] L. Bornmann, L. Leydesdorff, Does quality and content matter for citedness? A comparison with paratextual factors and over time, *Journal of Informetrics*, 9 (2015) 419-429.

[221] L. Bornmann, L. Leydesdorff, A comment on "Scientometrics in a changing research landscape" Response, *Embo Reports*, 16 (2015) 262-262.

[222] L. Bornmann, L. Leydesdorff, Topical connections between the institutions within an organisation (institutional co-authorships, direct citation links and co-citations), *Scientometrics*, 102 (2015) 455-463.

[223] L. Bornmann, L. Leydesdorff, Skewness of citation impact data and covariates of citation distributions: A large-scale empirical analysis based on Web of Science data, *Journal of Informetrics*, 11 (2017) 164-175.

[224] L. Bornmann, L. Leydesdorff, Count highly-cited papers instead of papers with h citations: use normalized citation counts and compare "like with like", *Scientometrics*, 115 (2018) 1119-1123.

[225] L. Bornmann, L. Leydesdorff, W. Marx, Citation environment of *Angewandte Chemie*, *Chimia*, 61 (2007) 104-109.

[226] L. Bornmann, L. Leydesdorff, R. Mutz, The use of percentiles and percentile rank classes in the analysis of bibliometric data: Opportunities and limits, *Journal of Informetrics*, 7 (2013) 158-165.

[227] L. Bornmann, L. Leydesdorff, P. Van den Besselaar, A meta-evaluation of scientific research proposals: Different ways of comparing rejected to awarded applications, *Journal of Informetrics*, 4 (2010) 211-220.

[228] L. Bornmann, L. Leydesdorff, C. Walch-Solimena, C. Ettl, Mapping excellence in the geography of science: An approach based on Scopus data, *Journal of Informetrics*, 5 (2011) 537-546.

[229] L. Bornmann, L. Leydesdorff, J. Wang, Which percentile-based approach should be preferred for calculating normalized citation impact values? An empirical comparison of five approaches including a newly developed citation-rank approach (P100), *Journal of Informetrics*, 7 (2013) 933-944.

[230] L. Bornmann, L. Leydesdorff, J. Wang, How to improve the prediction based on citation impact percentiles for years shortly after the publication date?, *Journal of Informetrics*, 8 (2014) 175-180.

[231] L. Bornmann, A. Tekles, L. Leydesdorff, How well does I3 perform for impact measurement compared to other bibliometric indicators? The convergent validity of several (field-normalized) indicators, *Scientometrics*, 119 (2019) 1187-1205.

[232] L. Bornmann, C. Wagner, L. Leydesdorff, BRICS countries and scientific excellence: A bibliometric analysis of most frequently cited papers, *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 66 (2015) 1507-1513.

[233] L. Bornmann, C. Wagner, L. Leydesdorff, The geography of references in elite articles: Which countries contribute to the archives of knowledge?, *PLoS One*, 13 (2018).

[234] T. Braun, Strange referencing and some remarks, *Scientometrics*, 63 (2005) 407-410.

[235] M. Callon, L. Leydesdorff, EVALUATION OF RESEARCH - HOW TO MAKE STATISTICS IMPACT - REPLY, *Recherche*, 18 (1987) 953-953.

[236] M. Callon, L. Leydesdorff, HOW HEALTHY IS RESEARCH IN FRANCE, *Recherche*, 18 (1987) 412-419.

[237] C.M. Chen, L. Leydesdorff, Patterns of Connections and Movements in Dual-Map Overlays: A New Method of Publication Portfolio Analysis, *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 65 (2014) 334-351.

[238] J.A. Comins, S.A. Carmack, L. Leydesdorff, Patent citation spectroscopy (PCS): Online retrieval of

- landmark patents based on an algorithmic approach, *Journal of Informetrics*, 12 (2018) 1223-1231.
- [239] J.A. Comins, L. Leydesdorff, RPYS i/o: software demonstration of a web-based tool for the historiography and visualization of citation classics, sleeping beauties and research fronts, *Scientometrics*, 107 (2016) 1509-1517.
- [240] J.A. Comins, L. Leydesdorff, Identification of Long-Term Concept-Symbols Among Citations: Do Common Intellectual Histories Structure Citation Behavior?, *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 68 (2017) 1224-1233.
- [241] J.A. Comins, L. Leydesdorff, Citation algorithms for identifying research milestones driving biomedical innovation, *Scientometrics*, 110 (2017) 1495-1504.
- [242] E.L. D'Antonio, M.S. Deinema, S.P. Kearns, T.A. Frey, S. Tanghe, K. Perry, T.A. Roy, H.S. Gracz, A. Rodriguez, J. D'Antonio, Structure-based approach to the identification of a novel group of selective glucosamine analogue inhibitors of *Trypanosoma cruzi* glucokinase, *Molecular and Biochemical Parasitology*, 204 (2015) 64-76.
- [243] W. de Nooy, L. Leydesdorff, The dynamics of triads in aggregated journal-journal citation relations: Specialty developments at the above-journal level, *Journal of Informetrics*, 9 (2015) 542-554.
- [244] M. Deinema, L. Leydesdorff, The two faces of American power - Military and political communication during the Cuban missile crisis, *Kybernetes*, 35 (2006) 547-566.
- [245] W. Dolfsma, L. Leydesdorff, 'Medium-tech' industries may be of greater importance to a local economy than 'High-tech' firms: New methods for measuring the knowledge base of an economic system, *Med. Hypotheses*, 71 (2008) 330-334.
- [246] W. Dolfsma, L. Leydesdorff, Lock-in and break-out from technological trajectories: Modeling and policy implications, *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 76 (2009) 932-941.
- [247] W. Dolfsma, L. Leydesdorff, The citation field of evolutionary economics, *Journal of Evolutionary Economics*, 20 (2010) 645-664.
- [248] W. Dolfsma, L. Leydesdorff, Innovation systems as patent networks: The Netherlands, India and nanotech, *Innov.-Manag. Policy Pract.*, 13 (2011) 311-326.
- [249] L. Egghe, L. Leydesdorff, The Relation Between Pearson's Correlation Coefficient r and Salton's Cosine Measure, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 60 (2009) 1027-1036.
- [250] H. Etzkowitz, L. Leydesdorff, A triple helix of academic-industry-government relations: Development models beyond 'capitalism versus socialism', *Curr. Sci.*, 70 (1996) 690-693.
- [251] H. Etzkowitz, L. Leydesdorff, The endless transition: A "triple helix" of university-industry-government relations, *Minerva*, 36 (1998) 203-208.
- [252] H. Etzkowitz, L. Leydesdorff, The dynamics of innovation: from National Systems and "Mode 2" to a Triple Helix of university-industry-government relations, *Research Policy*, 29 (2000) 109-123.
- [253] K. Frenken, L. Leydesdorff, Scaling trajectories in civil aircraft (1913-1997), *Research Policy*, 29 (2000) 331-348.
- [254] Y. Fujigaki, L. Leydesdorff, Quality control and validation boundaries in a triple helix of university-industry-government: "Mode 2" and the future of university research, *Social Science Information Sur Les Sciences Sociales*, 39 (2000) 635-655.
- [255] R.L. Goldstone, L. Leydesdorff, The import and export of Cognitive Science, *Cognitive Science*, 30 (2006) 983-993.
- [256] W. Halffman, L. Leydesdorff, Is Inequality Among Universities Increasing? Gini Coefficients and the Elusive Rise of Elite Universities, *Minerva*, 48 (2010) 55-72.
- [257] R. Haunschild, L. Leydesdorff, L. Bornmann, I. Hellsten, W. Marx, Does the public discuss other topics on climate change than researchers? A comparison of explorative networks based on author keywords and hashtags, *Journal of Informetrics*, 13 (2019) 695-707.
- [258] T. Hecking, L. Leydesdorff, Can topic models be used in research evaluations? Reproducibility, validity, and reliability when compared with semantic maps, *Res. Evaluat.*, 28 (2019) 263-272.
- [259] G. Heimeriks, L. Leydesdorff, Emerging search regimes: measuring co-evolutions among research, science, and society, *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*, 24 (2012) 51-67.
- [260] I. Hellsten, J. Dawson, L. Leydesdorff, Implicit media frames: Automated analysis of public debate on artificial sweeteners, *Public Underst. Sci.*, 19 (2010) 590-608.
- [261] I. Hellsten, L. Leydesdorff, The construction of interdisciplinarity: The development of the knowledge

- base and programmatic focus of the journal *ClimaticChange*, 1977-2013, *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 67 (2016) 2181-2193.
- [262] I. Hellsten, L. Leydesdorff, P. Wouters, Multiple presents: how search engines rewrite the past, *New Media & Society*, 8 (2006) 901-924.
- [263] X.J. Hu, L. Leydesdorff, R. Rousseau, Heterogeneity in an undirected network: Definition and measurement, *Journal of Informetrics*, 11 (2017) 669-682.
- [264] I. Ivanova, O. Strand, D. Kushnir, L. Leydesdorff, Economic and technological complexity: A model study of indicators of knowledge-based innovation systems, *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 120 (2017) 77-89.
- [265] I.A. Ivanova, L. Leydesdorff, Rotational symmetry and the transformation of innovation systems in a Triple Helix of university-industry-government relations, *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 86 (2014) 143-156.
- [266] I.A. Ivanova, L. Leydesdorff, A simulation model of the Triple Helix of university-industry-government relations and the decomposition of the redundancy, *Scientometrics*, 99 (2014) 927-948.
- [267] I.A. Ivanova, L. Leydesdorff, Knowledge-generating efficiency in innovation systems: The acceleration of technological paradigm changes with increasing complexity, *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 96 (2015) 254-265.
- [268] M.W. Johnson, L. Leydesdorff, Beer's Viable System Model and Luhmann's Communication Theory: 'Organizations' from the Perspective of Meta-Games, *Systems Research and Behavioral Science*, 32 (2015) 266-282.
- [269] D.F. Kogler, G. Heimeriks, L. Leydesdorff, Patent portfolio analysis of cities: statistics and maps of technological inventiveness, *European Planning Studies*, 26 (2018) 2256-2278.
- [270] R.N. Kostoff, J.A. del Rio, H.D. Cortes, C. Smith, A. Smith, C. Wagner, L. Leydesdorff, G. Karypis, G. Malpohl, R. Tshiteya, The structure and infrastructure of Mexico's science and technology, *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 72 (2005) 798-814.
- [271] R.N. Kostoff, J.A. del Rio, H.D. Cortes, C. Smith, A. Smith, C. Wagner, L. Leydesdorff, G. Karypis, G. Malpohl, R. Tshiteya, Clustering methodologies for identifying country core competencies, *Journal of Information Science*, 33 (2007) 21-40.
- [272] M. Kozak, L. Bornmann, L. Leydesdorff, How have the Eastern European countries of the former Warsaw Pact developed since 1990? A bibliometric study, *Scientometrics*, 102 (2015) 1101-1117.
- [273] E. Kranakis, L. Leydesdorff, TELETRAFFIC CONFERENCES - STUDYING A FIELD OF ENGINEERING SCIENCE, *Scientometrics*, 15 (1989) 563-591.
- [274] K. Kumpulainen, T. Lovat, P.A. Alexander, S.M. Loyens, P. Daly, D. Pnevmatikos, R.E. Mayer, F. Laevers, L. Heylen, L. Leydesdorff, S. Human-Vogel, About the outdated Newtonian paradigm in education and complexity and a complexity science of learning: How far are we from a paradigm shift?, *Educational Research Review*, 3 (2008) 77-100.
- [275] K.S. Kwon, H.W. Park, M. So, L. Leydesdorff, Has globalization strengthened South Korea's national research system? National and international dynamics of the Triple Helix of scientific co-authorship relationships in South Korea, *Scientometrics*, 90 (2012) 163-176.
- [276] B. Lengyel, L. Leydesdorff, Regional Innovation Systems in Hungary: The Failing Synergy at the National Level, *Regional Studies*, 45 (2011) 677-693.
- [277] B. Lengyel, T. Sebestyen, L. Leydesdorff, Challenges for regional innovation policies in Central and Eastern Europe: Spatial concentration and foreign control of US patenting, *Sci. Public Policy*, 42 (2015) 1-14.
- [278] L.Z. Li, L. Leydesdorff, S. Nioka, N.N. Sun, E. Garfield, Citation analysis of the scientific publications of Britton Chance in ISI citation indexes, *Journal of Innovative Optical Health Sciences*, 7 (2014).
- [279] D. Lucio-Arias, L. Leydesdorff, Knowledge emergence in scientific communication: from "fullerenes" to "nanotubes", *Scientometrics*, 70 (2007) 603-632.
- [280] D. Lucio-Arias, L. Leydesdorff, Main-path analysis and path-dependent transitions in HistCite (TM)-based historiograms, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 59 (2008) 1948-1962.
- [281] D. Lucio-Arias, L. Leydesdorff, An Indicator of Research Front Activity: Measuring Intellectual Organization as Uncertainty Reduction in Document Sets, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 60 (2009) 2488-2498.
- [282] D. Lucio-Arias, L. Leydesdorff, The dynamics of exchanges and references among scientific texts, and

- the autopoiesis of discursive knowledge, *Journal of Informetrics*, 3 (2009) 261-271.
- [283] W. Marx, L. Bornmann, A. Barth, L. Leydesdorff, Detecting the Historical Roots of Research Fields by Reference Publication Year Spectroscopy (RPYS), *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 65 (2014) 751-764.
- [284] S. Milojevic, L. Leydesdorff, Information metrics (iMetrics): a research specialty with a socio-cognitive identity?, *Scientometrics*, 95 (2013) 141-157.
- [285] J. Mingers, L. Leydesdorff, A review of theory and practice in scientometrics, *European Journal of Operational Research*, 246 (2015) 1-19.
- [286] J. Mingers, L. Leydesdorff, Identifying research fields within business and management: a journal cross-citation analysis, *Journal of the Operational Research Society*, 66 (2015) 1370-1384.
- [287] T. Opthof, L. Leydesdorff, Caveats for the journal and field normalizations in the CWTS ("Leiden") evaluations of research performance, *Journal of Informetrics*, 4 (2010) 423-430.
- [288] T. Opthof, L. Leydesdorff, A comment to the paper by Waltman et al., *Scientometrics*, 87, 467-481, 2011, *Scientometrics*, 88 (2011) 1011-1016.
- [289] J.R. Ozinga, The idea within: A story of scholarly blossoming in the Amsterdam spring, *Systems Research and Behavioral Science*, 19 (2002) 171-176.
- [290] H.W. Park, H.D. Hong, L. Leydesdorff, A comparison of the knowledge-based innovation systems in the economies of South Korea and the Netherlands using Triple Helix indicators, *Scientometrics*, 65 (2005) 3-27.
- [291] H.W. Park, L. Leydesdorff, Korean journals in the Science Citation Index: What do they reveal about the intellectual structure of S & T in Korea?, *Scientometrics*, 75 (2008) 439-462.
- [292] H.W. Park, L. Leydesdorff, Knowledge linkage structures in communication studies using citation analysis among communication journals, *Scientometrics*, 81 (2009) 157-175.
- [293] H.W. Park, L. Leydesdorff, Longitudinal trends in networks of university-industry-government relations in South Korea: The role of programmatic incentives, *Research Policy*, 39 (2010) 640-649.
- [294] H.W. Park, L. Leydesdorff, Decomposing social and semantic networks in emerging "big data" research, *Journal of Informetrics*, 7 (2013) 756-765.
- [295] H.W. Park, J. Yoon, L. Leydesdorff, The normalization of co-authorship networks in the bibliometric evaluation: the government stimulation programs of China and Korea, *Scientometrics*, 109 (2016) 1017-1036.
- [296] A.M. Petersen, D. Rotolo, L. Leydesdorff, A triple helix model of medical innovation: Supply, demand, and technological capabilities in terms of Medical Subject Headings, *Research Policy*, 45 (2016) 666-681.
- [297] I. Rafols, L. Leydesdorff, Content-Based and Algorithmic Classifications of Journals: Perspectives on the Dynamics of Scientific Communication and Indexer Effects, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 60 (2009) 1823-1835.
- [298] I. Rafols, L. Leydesdorff, A. O'Hare, P. Nightingale, A. Stirling, How journal rankings can suppress interdisciplinary research: A comparison between Innovation Studies and Business & Management, *Research Policy*, 41 (2012) 1262-1282.
- [299] I. Rafols, A.L. Porter, L. Leydesdorff, Science Overlay Maps: A New Tool for Research Policy and Library Management, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 61 (2010) 1871-1887.
- [300] A. Rahman, R. Guns, L. Leydesdorff, T.C.E. Engels, Measuring the match between evaluators and evaluatees: cognitive distances between panel members and research groups at the journal level, *Scientometrics*, 109 (2016) 1639-1663.
- [301] D. Rotolo, L. Leydesdorff, Matching Medline/PubMed data with Web of Science: A routine in R language, *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 66 (2015) 2155-2159.
- [302] D. Rotolo, I. Rafols, M.M. Hopkins, L. Leydesdorff, Strategic Intelligence on Emerging Technologies: Scientometric Overlay Mapping, *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 68 (2017) 214-233.
- [303] R.D. Shelton, L. Leydesdorff, Publish or Patent: Bibliometric Evidence For Empirical Trade-Offs in National Funding Strategies, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 63 (2012) 498-511.
- [304] A.L. Shi, L. Leydesdorff, What Do the Cited and Citing Environments Reveal about Advances in Atmospheric Physics?, *Advances in Atmospheric Sciences*, 28 (2011) 238-244.
- [305] O. Strand, I. Ivanova, L. Leydesdorff, Decomposing the Triple-Helix synergy into the regional

- innovation systems of Norway: firm data and patent networks, *Quality & Quantity*, 51 (2017) 963-988.
- [306] O. Strand, L. Leydesdorff, Where is synergy indicated in the Norwegian innovation system? Triple-Helix relations among technology, organization, and geography, *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 80 (2013) 471-484.
- [307] A. Thor, W. Marx, L. Leydesdorff, L. Bornmann, New features of CitedReferencesExplorer (CRExplorer), *Scientometrics*, 109 (2016) 2049-2051.
- [308] A. Thor, W. Marx, L. Leydesdorff, L. Bornmann, Introducing CitedReferencesExplorer (CRExplorer): A program for reference publication year spectroscopy with cited references standardization, *Journal of Informetrics*, 10 (2016) 503-515.
- [309] P. van den Besselaar, L. Bornmann, L. Leydesdorff, Untitled, *Journal of Informetrics*, 8 (2014) 801-801.
- [310] P. van den Besselaar, L. Leydesdorff, Mapping change in scientific specialties: A scientometric reconstruction of the development of artificial intelligence, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science*, 47 (1996) 415-436.
- [311] P. van den Besselaar, L. Leydesdorff, Past performance, peer review and project selection: a case study in the social and behavioral sciences, *Res. Evaluat.*, 18 (2009) 273-288.
- [312] P. van den Besselaar, L. Leydesdorff, Past performance, peer review, and project selection: A case study in the social and behavioural sciences (vol 18, pg 273, 2009), *Res. Evaluat.*, 23 (2014) 381-381.
- [313] B. van Heur, L. Leydesdorff, S. Wyatt, Turning to ontology in STS? Turning to STS through 'ontology', *Social Studies of Science*, 43 (2013) 341-362.
- [314] B. Vandermeulen, L. Leydesdorff, HAS THE STUDY OF PHILOSOPHY AT DUTCH UNIVERSITIES CHANGED UNDER ECONOMIC AND POLITICAL PRESSURES, *Sci. Technol. Hum. Values*, 16 (1991) 288-321.
- [315] B. Vandermeulen, A. Roozen, L. Leydesdorff, DID KNOWLEDGE STRUCTURES IN THE STUDY OF PHILOSOPHY AT DUTCH UNIVERSITIES CHANGE UNDER ECONOMIC AND POLITICAL PRESSURES, *Sci. Technol. Hum. Values*, 13 (1988) 190-190.
- [316] G. Velez-Cuartas, D. Lucio-Arias, L. Leydesdorff, REGIONAL AND GLOBAL SCIENCE: PUBLICATIONS FROM LATIN AMERICA AND THE CARIBBEAN IN THE SCIELO CITATION INDEX AND THE WEB OF SCIENCE, *Prof. Inf.*, 25 (2016) 35-46.
- [317] M. Venditti, E. Reale, L. Leydesdorff, Disclosure of university research to third parties: A non-market perspective on an Italian university, *Sci. Public Policy*, 40 (2013) 792-800.
- [318] M.R. Vilanova, L. Leydesdorff, Why Catalonia cannot be considered as a regional innovation system, *Scientometrics*, 50 (2001) 215-240.
- [319] C.S. Wagner, L. Bornmann, L. Leydesdorff, Recent Developments in China-US Cooperation in Science, *Minerva*, 53 (2015) 199-214.
- [320] C.S. Wagner, L. Leydesdorff, Seismology as a dynamic, distributed area of scientific research, *Scientometrics*, 58 (2003) 91-114.
- [321] C.S. Wagner, L. Leydesdorff, Network structure, self-organization, and the growth of international collaboration in science, *Research Policy*, 34 (2005) 1608-1618.
- [322] C.S. Wagner, L. Leydesdorff, An Integrated Impact Indicator: A new definition of 'Impact' with policy relevance, *Res. Evaluat.*, 21 (2012) 183-188.
- [323] C.S. Wagner, H.W. Park, L. Leydesdorff, The Continuing Growth of Global Cooperation Networks in Research: A Conundrum for National Governments, *PLoS One*, 10 (2015).
- [324] C.S. Wagner, T.A. Whetsell, L. Leydesdorff, Growth of international collaboration in science: revisiting six specialties, *Scientometrics*, 110 (2017) 1633-1652.
- [325] P. Wouters, L. Leydesdorff, HAS PRICE DREAM COME TRUE - IS SCIENTOMETRICS A HARD SCIENCE, *Scientometrics*, 31 (1994) 193-222.
- [326] P. Wouters, L. Leydesdorff, Proceedings of the Erasmus Workshop on Quantitative Approaches to Science & Technology Studies - Amsterdam, 21-24 May 1996 - Introduction, *Scientometrics*, 38 (1997) 3-5.
- [327] E. Yan, Y. Ding, B. Cronin, L. Leydesdorff, A bird's-eye view of scientific trading: Dependency relations among fields of science, *Journal of Informetrics*, 7 (2013) 249-264.
- [328] F.Y. Ye, L. Leydesdorff, The "Academic Trace" of the Performance Matrix: A Mathematical Synthesis of the h-Index and the Integrated Impact Indicator (I₃), *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 65 (2014) 742-750.
- [329] F.Y. Ye, S.S. Yu, L. Leydesdorff, The Triple Helix of University-Industry-Government Relations at the

- Country Level and Its Dynamic Evolution Under the Pressures of Globalization, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 64 (2013) 2317-2325.
- [330] A. Zelman, L. Leydesdorff, Threaded email messages in Self-Organization and Science & Technology Studies oriented mailing lists, *Scientometrics*, 48 (2000) 361-380.
- [331] P. Zhou, L. Leydesdorff, The emergence of China as a leading nation in science, *Research Policy*, 35 (2006) 83-104.
- [332] P. Zhou, L. Leydesdorff, The citation impacts and citation environments of Chinese journals in mathematics, *Scientometrics*, 72 (2007) 185-200.
- [333] P. Zhou, L. Leydesdorff, A comparison between the China Scientific and Technical Papers and Citations Database and the Science Citation Index in terms of journal hierarchies and interjournal citation relations, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 58 (2007) 223-236.
- [334] P. Zhou, L. Leydesdorff, Chemistry in China - a bibliometric view, *Chim. Oggi-Chem. Today*, 27 (2009) 19-22.
- [335] P. Zhou, L. Leydesdorff, Fractional counting of citations in research evaluation: A cross- and interdisciplinary assessment of the Tsinghua University in Beijing, *Journal of Informetrics*, 5 (2011) 360-368.
- [336] P. Zhou, X.N. Su, L. Leydesdorff, A Comparative Study on Communication Structures of Chinese Journals in the Social Sciences, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 61 (2010) 1360-1376.
- [337] P. Zhou, R. Tijssen, L. Leydesdorff, University-Industry Collaboration in China and the USA: A Bibliometric Comparison, *PLoS One*, 11 (2016).
- [338] Q.J. Zhou, L. Leydesdorff, The normalization of occurrence and Co-occurrence matrices in bibliometrics using Cosine similarities and Ochiai coefficients, *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 67 (2016) 2805-2814.